

Economic Analysis Of The Rural Social Security System In China

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Abstract

I propose an economic analysis of the China's rural social security system. The article takes a snapshot of the gradual changes underwent in the rural medium, replacement of family and land security with a modern system based on social funds and democratic management. Some ideas developed are: necessity and urgency of the social security system under new conditions of rural development in China, pros and cons; current situation and main problems of rural social security, plus the perspectives. It offers suggestions and possible solutions in drafting some principles for the foundation to reform the rural social security system in China.

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Key words: social security, government, system, economic analysis

1. Introduction

Setting up a social security system in the rural area of China is one of the most important steps in building a new type of socialist village. A rural environment contributing to the image of China's economic system, permanently on the verge between the principles of market economy, as imposed by the required alignment to the world's economy standards, and the communist principles of the government. Theoretically, the establishment of a social security system implies wellbeing and helps to increasing the living standard of people in disadvantaged areas, especially as China's sustained growth of the last decades supports social security expenses in the rural environment.

As for the state of those rural areas, family protection and the role of land are impaired by the fact that many inhabitants of rural areas abandon fieldwork and prefer taking jobs in urban areas, where the salary is much higher for a similar amount of work. All this process entails the aging of rural population.

2. The Required and Urgent Implementation of the Social Security System - pros and cons

Opinions regarding the social security system in rural China are currently divergent. Those arguing against the social security system in the rural environment state that:

- a. "For more than 1,000 years, Chinese farmers have catered for their security by means of their land and family and are able to live well even without this social security system, keeping their old habits" (Zheng 2002), even though the system of the "five guarantees" (Dong 2009) and the system of medical cooperation and care with collective funds and other government investments were implemented in the rural area in order to maintain social security.
- b. A high social security level in China is impossible to achieve in an advanced development state, as financial resources are limited and the social structure is weak. "There are currently more than 800 million farmers in the rural area and if their living standard is improved by means of a social security system, the government will be unable to take this financial burden and will, hence, impose limits to social security in the urban environment." (Cheung 2008) The difficult situation of some Western European countries is determined by a mismatch between the social security level and economic growth and is a strong argument for the idea that the Chinese government should also maintain an optimal financing of rural wellbeing.
- c. The social security system in the rural area will inevitably increase the social guarantee fund, resulting in a decrease in deposits and investments and affecting capital accumulation and development rates.

All these negative effects resulted in the government's failure to implement a firm resolution on the development of the social security system in the rural area.

Those approving of the security system in the rural area claim that:

- a. The social security measures to be implemented by the government shall result in: social safety, social equity, economic stimulation, cost management, generational redistribution and market economy development. A top-notch social security system is highly important for a country whose economic system and social structure were reformed in time.

- b. Income gaps between the rural environment and urban environment currently affect social stability. “According to the data provided by a group of researchers of the Institute of Economics of the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, the Gini index was 0.45 in China in 2002, more than 0.4 (the average world index), with income gaps between the rural and the urban environment soaring from 36% in 1995 to 43% in 2002. As for social security expenses, 10% were allocated to the population in the rural environment (60% of China’s total population) and 90% to the population in the urban environment (only 40% of China’s total population).” (Zheng 2002) This is unfair for farmers.
- c. The goal of social security is to achieve equality, by transferring taxes from the poor to the rich people, by providing a proper legislation, reducing conflicts, maintaining social order and ensuring a proper operation of economy and society. The establishment of a social security system in the rural area, which is a problem for more than 60% of China’s population, would mean the construction of a rural environment aligned to updated international development trends, but maintaining the central control specific to the communist administration. Helping rural disadvantaged areas is, in fact, a highly important issue for the development of the entire Chinese society. If differences between rural and urban living standards grow deeper and more neglected and the social security system is not implemented, so as to bring about a net increase of income, the Chinese economic system will be at risk in the long term.

Bottom line, the economic level and limited financial resources cannot represent a sufficient reason for a more urgent achievement of an advanced social security system, as soon as possible. The policy for solving imbalances between the rural and urban environments must be upgraded.

Analyzing the situation of the social security system in China between 2004 and 2008 (Table 1), I support the implementation of the social security system in the rural area.

Table 1. Situation of the social security system in China between 2004 and 2008

	Total social insurance (billions Yuan)	Pension (billions Yuan)	Medical insurance (billions Yuan)	Unemployment insurance (billions Yuan)	Labour accident insurance (billions Yuan)	Maternity insurance (billions Yuan)
2004						
No. of taxpayers (M)		165.53	124.04	105.84	68.45	43.84
Budget revenues	-	425.8	114.1	29.1	5.8	3.2
Annual growth percentage	-	15.7%	28.1%	15.8%	55.1%	24%
Budget expenses	-	350.2	86.2	21.1	3.3	1.9
Annual growth percentage	-	12.2%	31.6%	4.1%	22.9%	39.3%
2005						
No. of taxpayers (M)		174.87	137.83	106.48	84.8	54.08
Budget revenues	-	509.3	140.5	33.3	9.3	4.4
Annual growth percentage	-	19.6%	23.2%	13.8%	58.7%	37.5%
Budget expenses	-	404	107.9	20.7	4.8	2.7
Annual growth percentage	-	15.4%	25.2%	3%	42.7%	42.1%
2006						
No. of taxpayers (M)		187.66	157.32	111.87	102.68	64.59
Budget revenues	-	631	174.7	38.5	12.2	6.2
Annual growth percentage	-	23.9%	24.3%	15.8%	31.7%	41.9%
Budget expenses	-	489.7	127.7	19.3	6.85	3.7
Annual growth percentage	-	21.2%	18.3%	-6.9%	44.2%	36.8%
2007						
No. of taxpayers (M)		253.08	223.11	116.45	121.73	77.75
Budget revenues	1081.2	783.4	225.7	47.2	16.6	8.4

	Total social insurance (billions Yuan)	Pension (billions Yuan)	Medical insurance (billions Yuan)	Unemployment insurance (billions Yuan)	Labour accident insurance (billions Yuan)	Maternity insurance (billions Yuan)
Annual growth percentage	25.1%	24.2%	29.2%	17.5%	35.9%	34.5%
Budget expenses	788.8	596.5	156.2	21.8	8.8	5.6
Annual growth percentage	21.8%	21.8%	22.3%	9%	28.4%	48.4%
2008 No. of taxpayers (M)		274.86	318.22	124	137.87	92.54
Budget revenues	1369.6	974	304	58.5	21.7	11.4
Annual growth percentage	26.7%	24.3%	34.7%	24%	30.9%	36%
Budget expenses	992.5	739	208.4	25.4	12.7	7.1
Annual growth percentage	25.8%	23.9%	33.4%	16.5%	44.4%	28.6%

Source: Issued by the author

1. For a chronological economic analysis of the social security system, the reports of the National Bureau of Statistics of China were considered, for the years 2004-2008. Analysing this data, it was seen that social security in China has developed, starting 2004, when in the pension segment the number of taxpayers was 165.53 millions, till 2008, when the number of participants to pension programmes increased to 274.86 millions. Incomes to the pension budget increased significantly from one year to another: in 2004 the growth rate from the previous year was only 15%, whereas in 2008 it was 24.3%. Given the increase of incomes to the pension budget, from 425.8 billions Yuan (2004) to 974 billions Yuan (2008), i.e. double in only 5 years, it is my belief that we are witnessing a spectacular increase of social security in China.

2. In the medical insurance sector, the number of taxpayers increased from 124.04 million in 2004 to 318.22 million in 2008, i.e. an increase by more than 156% in only 5 years. This proves that there has been significant progress as for the population covered by this insurance. As for revenues in this segment, during 2004-2008, incomes soared from 114.1 billions Yuan to 304 billions Yuan, i.e. by more than 166% in only 5 years. Progresses in this segment will improve the general health state of the population, including in the rural area, where most of the elderly people (aged 65 and more) live.

3. Another segment I analysed regards unemployment insurance. The number of taxpayers in this sector increased from 105.84 millions persons in 2004 to 124 millions persons in 2008, i.e. an increase by only 17.29% in these 5 years. Although the increase in the number of taxpayers was not significant, incomes for this type of insurance doubled from 29.1 billions Yuan in 2004 to 58.5 billions Yuan in 2008. This increase in revenues resulted in an increase of unemployment aid and, hence, to higher social security in the urban and rural areas of China.

4. The total number of inhabitants participating in labour accident insurance increased from 68.45 million persons in 2004 to 137.87 million persons in 2008, which means that the number of persons participating in this type of insurance doubled in only 5 years. Revenues also underwent a significant increase in this period, from 5.8 billion Yuan to 21.7 billion Yuan, i.e. an increase of more than 274%. In my opinion, this spectacular increase in the number of persons and revenues enhances the protection against labour accidents both in the rural and the urban environment.

5. The number of inhabitants covered by maternity insurance increased from 43.84 million persons in 2004 to 92.54 million persons in 2008, i.e. it doubled in only 5 years. Revenues to the maternity insurance fund also increased considerably, from 3.2 billion Yuan in 2004 to 11.4 billion Yuan in 2008 (by more than 256% in this period). The spread of maternity insurance across Chinese population and the spectacular growth of budget revenues prove the ever increasing importance of this type of insurance, as a means of social security, both in the rural and urban areas.

I believe that the data in the table strongly supports social security by modern means (social security budgets) and the waiver of traditional means (the family and the land in the rural area). The annual growth percentages presented in the table for each social insurance programme confirm, in my opinion, the stability and the positive evolution of the Chinese social security system.

According to the above analysis, the social security construction in the rural environment has both positive and negative effects. Considering the current economic, political and social situation, the positive effect is much stronger than the negative one.

2.1. The Urgency of Advancement for the Social Security System in Today's Rural Development Context

The land's security function disappears gradually. Farmers' lives are usually based on land, but, due to long term management contracts and urbanisation, agricultural fields have decreased to about 0.68 sq km/person. This reduction, combined with the price impact after the accession to the WTO (World Trade Organisation) in December 2001, resulted in the farmers' impossibility to cater for their daily necessities solely based on land. A major part of a farmer's revenues proceed from non-agricultural production and their dependency on the land keeps decreasing. People who lose land face major issues in supporting themselves, after they use up the indemnification for the public use of the land. This is now becoming a prominent issue.

The family's security function weakens as the number of family members decreases. The care of elderly people has depended on the family in the rural areas for a long time. The so-called belief that "more children means more security", specific to the Chinese rural environment, means that more children more easily manage to support two aging parents. Now, given the implementation of the birth control policy, each family may have two children at most. Under these conditions, a child finds it very difficult to support both a parent and his/her own costs. The family structure in villages is more and more unstable and entire families get condemned to poverty because of the disease of an individual. In urbanisation, the social security of working peasants is uncertain. "According to the statistics of the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture, by the end of 2002, the rural population working in cities was 94 million, added to 130 million employees in rural companies" (Li 2005). This means a total of 224 million persons, i.e. more than $\frac{1}{4}$ of the rural population worked in non-traditional fields. Moreover, this category of farmers is the main workforce of families. Their urban incomes have exceeded their agricultural incomes. They make up a huge social group. They are often involved in hazardous jobs and a family may lose its single source of support in case of illness or disability of such an individual.

Aging population is increasing in the rural area. "In 2000, the rural population was 833 million and elderly people (aged 65 and more) represented 7.36% of the total, while only 6.29% of the urban population. More than 75% of China's elderly people live in the rural area." (Yan 2001) The aging speed in the rural area is quicker than in cities, due to the birth prevention policy and the migration of young workers from villages to cities. This means that the burden of taking care of old people gets harder and a proper social security system should be urgently set up. According to the above analysis, the scarce social security in the rural environment prevented the development of agriculture and economy. The central factor of the new socialist construction of the rural area lies in solving village issues. Thus, the construction of rural social security must be accelerated.

3. The Current Situation and the Main Issues of Rural Social Security

3.1. The Current Status of Rural Social Security

Rural social security is primarily autonomous and provides minimal guarantees insured by the rural security system, as depending on collective economy. The main implemented systems include:

- a. "The five rural guarantees": a social aid system supporting children with no voluntary alimony and disabled elderly people.
- b. The new medical system of rural cooperative services: it started in 1956, it was then interrupted for various reasons and in 1997 it restarted, after the Chinese Central Committee issued the "Decision on Hygiene Reform and Development". However, big gaps were found in fund collection, expense compensation, management and coverage. "In 2003, national pilot programmes of the new medical system of rural cooperative services were set up. By the end of 2005, 641 districts did this. There were 160 million participants in cooperative medical services, covering 225 million farmers."(Newsweek,February 15th,2006)
- c. The minimum social security level in rural areas. Starting 1997, some rural areas with better economic conditions gradually established a minimum social security level. Those who did not meet the lowest local living standard could get a subsidy from the financial department, in order to make up for the difference. By the end of 2004, 8 provinces, including Beijing, Shanghai, Zhejiang, set up this system, covering 1,206 districts and 4.9637 million people.

3.2. The Main Issue in the Construction of Rural Social Security

Diverging opinions. Government officials and academic experts currently have different views on the importance and necessity of setting up the social security system in the rural area. Many people think that such a system is important, but not very urgent, and the traditional security of land and family should continue playing a major part, as the government cannot set up a homogeneous social security system in the entire country. This major gap causes continuous arguments on the framework and purpose of the security system, with the rural social security system remaining under the level achieved in central planning in the 50s,

as a mere target subordinated to political and social stability, not an independent construction based on its own principles and likely to be treated as a whole.

The Chinese rural social security system is not complete. The full rural social security system should include: social aids, social maintenance and special and favoured treatment. In fact, its current content has a single element: subsidy as an aid. The system of the “five guarantees” is a social aid system with funds proceeding from collective accumulation, not national financial subsidies. Moreover, the minimum social security level is only implemented in some provinces with developed economy. Social security as a basic element includes some provinces with a developed economy. Social security as a basic element includes aged people policies, medical care, unemployment insurance, injury benefits, disability benefits, etc. However, until 2005 social security in the rural areas only included rural medical care cooperatives, with the other fields being left empty. Moreover, it only covered a limited area, with a limited number of participants, at a low standard. For instance, cooperative medical care “covered about 17% of the rural population and only 24% of the country’s area”. (China Population Statistical Yearbook 2004). As for unemployment aids, except for some areas with better economic conditions, where collective unemployment aids had been implemented, and the central unemployment aid project did not exist. The special care system was especially targeted to the relatives of military staff and had a very restricted coverage.

The slow increase in farmers’ revenues restricted the evolution of the rural social security system. On the one hand, the low level of revenues restricted the effective demand of rural social security and the social security provided by the government. On the other hand, it also resulted in a low consumption, restricting the participation in the social security system. The withdrawal from the system of some working peasants was seen in the Guangdong province, proving to some extent the negative effect of small revenues on farmers’ conscience and enthusiasm.

4. Countermeasures and Suggestions

The 11th five-year plan was crucial for China to set up a new rural socialist construction and accelerate the advancement of a wellbeing society in the rural environment. Hence, it is very difficult to support the wellbeing of farmers and their rights, to achieve major economic and social progress in the rural environment, by improving rural social security, given the large revenue gaps between the rural and the urban area and the increase in development lags. This is why I consider that the following principles and systems should currently converge:

4.1. Establishing the Principles of the Rural Social Security Reform

Treating the rural and urban environments as a whole. First and foremost, adopting the general conception. Social security is an essentially planned arrangement, so rural social security must be planned as an improvement of socialist market economy and seen as a new strong incentive for building a rural area, with prospects for making up delays from the urban area. Secondly, the social security goal may be maintaining a reasonable level of revenues both in the rural and urban area, so that sustainable development may be possible. Thirdly, following a correct chronology, as conditioned by the limited financial resources of the country and farmers’ small revenues, in this phase, the construction of social security should focus on the economic and social development of these areas. The Chinese Central Committee proposed “the increase of social security expenses, continuing agricultural investments, according to the moderate amount rule and gradual increase, continuing infrastructure investments and a focus on the rural area”. Moreover, this should be implemented according to the level of economy and revenues in different areas. In my opinion, we should make a difference between the purpose and the process of the construction and understand that, for the moment, the most important is the security against serious diseases for elderly and low income people.

The principles of equity and efficiency. The essential function of social security is to supply basic security and a relatively correct distribution, by adjusting re-distribution. Correctness is found from three points of view. First, the social security fund should gradually focus on the rural area, in order to balance the expense gap between the urban and rural environments. The second aspect, in my opinion, is that the rural social security system should cover all the rural population to an equal extent. The third aspect deals with the implementation process, which should be public, fair and supervised, from my point of view. However, if the rural social security system cannot focus on correctness exclusively and system planning is inappropriate, this may have an impact on efficiency. The efficiency rule includes three aspects. First, motivating individual activity and calling farmers to acquiring wealth by work. High social aids for an entire lifetime, in a minority of developed villages and cities, may reduce a farmer’s enthusiasm of acquiring wealth by his/her own efforts to a certain extent and creates a wide range of social issues. The second is to encourage individual savings. Social security must be suitable to such savings, as it cannot merely encourage individual activity and replace the lack of capital caused by increasing social security payments, which take up financial accumulation. The third is to decrease management costs and improve management efficiency. Management sections must merge in order to avoid management with several senior authorities and reduce administrative layers. Social security fund management should include trade

investment organisations competing for improving the fund's return rate. Due to the orderly development of correctness and efficiency, rural social security must be made so as to combine correctness and efficiency.

4.2. The Focus of the Construction of the Current Rural Social Security System

4.2.1. Establishing the Moderate Security of Pensions

While land and family keep acting as a security, the government, the village community and the individual ratios in retirement pensions should be determined reasonably. Subsidies to individual accounts should also increase gradually, provided that the community and the individual support major expenses. At the same time, the government should bring insurance and its benefits to the farmers' attention. The pension should be established depending on the individual's contribution, in order to encourage people with high income to pay higher pension contributions. This is also favourable for decreasing the fund scale.

Another idea to improve the situation would be connecting pension security in the rural and urban environment and breaking labour flow barriers imposed by the different types of social security between the city and the rural area. Based on personal accounts, the efficiency of resources' availability may be promoted with a better labour fluidity, by conversion of the rural and urban pension accounts. It is thought that various levels of social security should exist for various groups, such as: peasants, working peasants, farmers with no land, farmers in small towns, etc. However, I consider that the distinct status and type of a farmer will be hard to establish and confirm, thus increasing coordination and management costs.

4.2.2. Accelerating the Rural Medical Insurance Construction

Setting up medical insurance against serious illnesses. Currently, the highest hazard of farmers is that a serious illness of one individual frequently impoverishes an entire family. This is why I think that a solid medical security system should be urgently set up, replacing the medical system of rural cooperative services and meeting needs better, with the same limited funds, but with better management. In my opinion, the key to setting up this system is the general management of the fund and its use according to the simplification, unification and efficiency rule, as well as a gradual connection to the urban medical insurance model.

Another important issue is the continued expansion of the new medical system in the rural area. Nowadays, this system is in an experimental phase, with a narrow coverage. The basis of financial resources contributing to the fund formation should be extended, in order to implement this system at a large scale. Supervision must be ensured, so as to determine high efficiency in the long run. The correct management of the relationship between the government and the market is very important to this purpose. A significant step was made in 2004, when the Xinxiang municipal government "authorised the Chinese life insurance company to operate the new rural medical system, which managed deposits of almost 100 millions RMB Yuan in medical funds, of more than 3.38 millions farmers". (Wang, Zhang 2007) It was the first time that the government did not act according to the traditional combined control and operation model of social security. This shows that the new model must be promoted as per the relevant laws and policies.

The farmers' capacity of accessing medical services should be improved by adjusting the social investment structure in order to increase the efficiency of the medical service organisation management and promote medical resources by competition between the offer and demand of medical services. At the same time, public health policies should be developed in order to maintain health and prevent diseases, with a view to reducing serious illnesses in the rural area.

References

- Cheung Steven – *The Economic System of China*- Arcadia Press Hong Kong 2008 pp 67
China Population Statistical Yearbook 2004
Dong K. – Medical insurance system evolution in China – Volume 20, *China Economic Review*, May 2009 pp 591-597
Li G.S – Farmer Differentiation and the Classification of Rural Social Security Construction-Local Finance Research 2005
National Bureau of Statistics of China:
http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/newsandcomingevents/t20090522_402560900.htm
http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/newsandcomingevents/t20080523_402482161.htm
http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/newsandcomingevents/t20070524_402406436.htm
http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/newsandcomingevents/t20060619_402331454.htm
http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/newsandcomingevents/t20050531_402253231.htm
Visit the Pilot New Rural Cooperative Medical Service. *Newsweek*, February 15th, 2006
Wang Bing, Zhang Jun - Economic Analysis of Social Security System in Today's China's Countryside – *China Population, Resources And Environment*-Volume 17, Issue 1, January 2007 pp 14-19
Yan L.W. - Who Will Care for the Aged Farmers in the 21st Century. *Economic Work* 2001, p 7
Zheng G. – *China Social Security Evolution and Evaluation* – China Remmin University Press Beijing 2002 pp 46-78